

8 Theory – Proving The Majestic (3) To be an Electron

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Abstract:

By using the equation the physical equation of the fine structure constant and the new framework 8-theory, we can find a simple and beautiful way to prove that the majestic (3) is an electron. The thesis of the theory proves it in the context of the Pauli Exclusion Principle and even amount of variations to vanish. The following is an additional way. that is the first time in all papers of 8 theory which two physical constants appear a priori, as the coupling constants values were derived mathematically in the thesis.

Introduction

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} = \frac{1}{128} \quad (1)$$

$$F_{V=0} = 8 + (1) \quad (2)$$

$$F_R\# = \left(8 * \prod_{V=1}^{V=R} N_V + (3) \right) + N_V = 30:128:850:9254.. \quad (3)$$

$$N_V = 2 \left(V + \frac{1}{2} \right); V \geq 0 \quad (4)$$

$$N_V \in \mathbb{P} \bigoplus (+1); \mathbb{P} \rightarrow \text{Set of Primes}$$

$$N_V = P_{max} \in [0, \mathbb{R}] \bigoplus (+1)$$

$$[(24 * 5) + (3)] + 5 \rightarrow \left[2N2 + \frac{1}{2} \right] + \frac{1}{2} \quad (5)$$

In the 8-theory framework, the electron is the majestic (3), and we can vary equation (1) to proof that is the case.

$$\frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \rightarrow \frac{3^2}{128} \quad (6)$$

Recall that arbitrary variations vanish in pairs of even numbers. That axiom in our framework related to fermions and allowed us to make a transformation regarding the strong interaction:

$$8 + (1) \rightarrow (1) \quad (7)$$

So we can vary (6) to prove that the majestic (3) is indeed an electron and solidify our theory and its validity:

$$\frac{3^2}{128} = \frac{8 + (1)}{128} \quad (8)$$

Even amount of variations taken to vanish so the final form of equation (8) is exactly like equation (1):

$$\frac{8 + (1)}{128} \rightarrow \frac{(1)}{128} = \frac{e^2}{\hbar c} \quad (9)$$

References

- [1] O. Manor. "The 8- Theory – The Theory of Everything" In: (2021)